

NON-DESTRUCTIVE CONTROL
OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES
BY SOFT X-RAY RADIOGRAPHY

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The usefulness of the radiographic technique to the examination of carbon fibre reinforced composites was investigated with soft X-rays. The exposure technique was established for the radiography of 2 and 3 mm thick samples. A constant mAmin technique was used, by which radiographs of an approximately constant density were produced on different brands of X-ray film and paper at voltages of 10 to 17 kV.

The quality of the radiographs was checked by using a step wedge and measuring density differences under it. Accuracy with which dimensions can be determined from the radiographs was checked by use of samples with thin tungsten wires. Defect detectability was investigated by examining the radiographs of samples with natural defects.

It was proved that low voltage radiography with soft X-rays is particularly suitable for the non-destructive examination of carbon fibre reinforced composites.

Introduction

Non-destructive Testing and Mechanical Properties

Carbon fibre reinforced plastics, as well as other fibrous composite materials, rely on their structural arrangement to achieve their mechanical properties. The fibres themselves are normally of little practical use, and only the well-designed combination of fibres and matrix can perform well and reliably in such demanding environments as those of e.g. airplanes and spacecrafts. The reliability of the material is dependent on the quality of the fabrication such that the designed properties are achieved, not only the best possible mechanical properties, but also any other (non-optimum) combination of properties, which may be designed for a specific purpose.

It is therefore of importance to be able to control the fabrication and to inspect the materials for their structural arrangements of fibres, matrix and defects.

The fibres contribute heavily to the mechanical properties, and their volume fraction, distribution, and arrangement are thus of prime importance for the composite properties. But also defects have, most often a detrimental, effect on the composite properties. The tensile properties, e.g. elastic modulus and strength of composites with continuous fibres, are normally affected little by voids and other defects, while the compressive and shear properties often will be affected seriously by relatively small fractions of voids. An often established variability of the mechanical properties of fibre composites, e.g. laminates, can in many cases be referred to a lack of information about the defect content, but of course also to incomplete knowledge about the fibres (distribution, volume fraction etc.).

For the practical and economical use of carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP), it is of great importance to know not only the defect content of the material but also the effect of this on the (mechanical) properties of the composite, so that acceptance of a component of CFRP can be judged on a sound and reliable basis.

A destructive testing of the mechanical properties is the most direct and safe method to establish the acceptance of a material. But it is, of course, desirable to use non-destructive testing and inspection to establish the soundness and acceptance of a component. There are two main areas for the NDT methods, firstly the inspection and control of the as fabricated component of CFRP, and secondly the inspection during service with the object of detecting any damage to the material and thus predict a safe rest-life of the component. For both fields of NDT the real interest lies with the mechanical properties of the material and the safe service of the component.

For the present investigation a convenient classification of defects has been adopted:

- matrix cracks, which may also be termed voids or porosities;
- fibre cracks;
- interface cracks, which may also be termed debonding;
- delamination, which refers to splitting between laminae in a laminate;
- inclusions, which refer to foreign bodies in the composite.

The total content of voids can be determined from a knowledge of the density of the composite and its volume fraction of fibres. This information is normally not sufficient for a safe prediction of (mechanical) behaviour. Quite often the void size, shape, distribution and position (in a laminate) will be important, because also the (local) stress field in the material will govern the effect of the voids on the overall mechanical properties of the CFRP.

The present study was undertaken to investigate the usefulness of X-ray radiography as a NDT method for CFRP materials, and to establish the experimental conditions of radiography, which will produce optimum radiographs. The study has been limited to voids and inclusions in the matrix of the CFRP, while other defects and their relationship with the mechanical properties will be the subject of later investigations.

We shall illustrate the importance of voids on the mechanical properties of CFRP with some examples from the literature.

Hancox [1] studied the compression strength of CFRP with 60 vol% fibres. Void contents up to 25 vol% were introduced and determined from measurement of the composite density and the volume fraction of fibres. At 10 vol% voids the strength was about 55% of the compression strength of the void-free material. The interlaminar shear strength was about 62%, and the flexural modulus was about 92% of the values of the void-free material, respectively. These data indicate the rather detrimental effect on the compression and the shear strengths, and the quite small effect on the flexural modulus. In a specific study of the shear properties of CFRP Hancox [2] found that at 4 vol% voids the shear modulus was 38% and the shear strength 30% of the values of the void-free material, respectively. Hancox found it difficult to relate theories for the void effect to the experiments, and attributed this mainly to lack of knowledge about the void size, shape and distribution. The voids were called "fine" and tended to be line defects, and they were often arranged in banded regions of dimensions 10 to 100 μm . The (total) void content was measured by ultrasonic techniques and found to agree with values obtained from density and fibre volume fraction, while assessment of the void content from polished sections, with the use of scanning microscopy, was unsuccessful.

This study shows that variability in and lack of knowledge about the void parameters makes it difficult to compare theories with experiments, and also to obtain consistent experimental data, which are important for empirical relations between strength and void content.

In a review of NDT methods for CFRP Stone [3] emphasises that the effect of defects in metals is rather well understood, while this is not the case for CFRP. Reliable NDT methods are needed, and X-ray radiography is considered valuable, but most likely in combination with other techniques, such as ultrasonics.

The lack of experience with the X-ray radiographic technique for CFRP materials is probably also illustrated by the initiation of research programmes, e.g. in Europe, on NDT methods and their relation to fatigue properties.

Previous Work on X-ray Radiography

A literature search was made to find some guidelines about the best radiographic technique suitable for CFRP. Unfortunately, the literature on the subject is very scarce and apparently no work has been reported on a systematic investigation of optimum radiographic conditions for the quality control of particular composites. Therefore it was necessary to investigate those factors contributing to the production of radiographs of good quality, which can be used for the assessment of CFRP.

In all the references studied on the subject, soft X-ray radiography, using beryllium window X-ray tubes, is recommended. In some special cases, as mentioned in [4], the betatron can be used. Use of penetrameters is also reported in the paper.

In three consecutive conferences on Composite Materials: Testing and Design of the American Society for Testing and Materials [5,6,7] some mention is made of the radiographic methods. In the paper [8] the alignment and distribution of the reinforcing phase has been checked with radiography, but no details of the technique are given.

In [9] some radiographs of fatigue and creep tested samples are reproduced, but without details of the radiographic technique. The same applies to [10] where an X-ray micrograph shows the development of fatigue shear cracks. Another paper [11] in [6] on boron/aluminium composites gives two X-ray micrographs of the fracture area without specifying the radiographic technique.

High magnification examination of X-ray images of fibre fractures is reported in [12], but no details are given neither about the radiographic technique nor the magnification examination.

In a symposium on Analysis of the Test Methods for High Modulus Fibres and Composites [13] two papers are devoted to non-destructive characterisation of composites, but they deal only with the ultrasonic technique.

Some information about the radiographic procedure is enclosed in the symposium on Composite Reliability [14]. A special X-ray non-destructive testing technique is described in [15] for the study of matrix cracks parallel to fibres and delaminations between plies in graphite-epoxy laminates. A 110 kV X-ray machine with a beryllium window tube was used; radiographs were taken on Kodak M films, and an opaque additive, tetrabromoethane, was used to enhance the image of the delaminations and voids. The same opaque compound was used in [16] to detect surface-connected defects, but no details about the radiographic technique itself are given.

An X-ray method using high resolution glass photographic plates and a magnification technique of X-ray images obtained on those plates is reported in [17].

It could be expected that the subject of non-destructive control of composite materials would be given appreciable attention in the papers presented to the first International Conference on Composite Materials [18]. Unfortunately, this was not the case. Therefore one can well understand the remark included into the rapporteur's report of the session Testing of Composite Materials [19]: "It was somewhat disappointing that so few papers contributed to the technology of non-destructive evaluation of composites, a subject the rapporteur feels is an area, which requires considerable development".

In the proceedings of the conference only three X-ray pictures could be found: two in the papers of the session on testing [20,21] and one in a paper of the session on applications [22], but no details about the X-ray techniques were given.

During the Eight World Conference on Non-destructive Testing [23] a special session was devoted to the testing of composite materials. Of the ten papers of this session four contain some information about radiographic testing [24,25,26,27], and one of these is entirely devoted to radiography of glass fibre reinforced plastic [27]. In [24,25,27] application of soft X-ray radiography is reported.

The radiographic control of boron/epoxy structures was performed on Kodak M film with a beryllium window 2.5 mm focal spot tube at a distance of 3 m [24], for the detection of moisture and damage in conventional honeycomb structures.

Radiography using soft X-rays or gamma-rays (5-30 keV) was used [25] to control the glass reinforcement of a laminate.

In [26] it is stated that conventional non-destructive testing methods for metals, such as radiography, ultrasonics and eddy currents, have been relatively unsuccessful in detecting localised matrix damage in carbon and glass fibre reinforced plastics. Specimens of those materials treated with a radiographically opaque penetrant clearly showed cracks longer than about 100 mm, but cracks less than 30 mm were not detected.

The paper presented by a manufacturer of X-ray apparatus (Balteau) [27] contained more details about the radiographic technique. Specimens in the thickness range from 1 to 25 mm were examined with soft X-rays from a beryllium window 0.5 mm focus tube at voltages below 50 kV. Fine grain X-ray films, such as Agfa-Gevaert D4 and D2 or Kodak M and R, were used, for which the internal unsharpness is not greater than 0.05 mm. For special cases the single coated D2 film was used. An exposure chart for the Balteau CE 50/10 constant potential X-ray machine was given.

The literature search shows the potentials of radiography in the quality control of reinforced composites. The scarcity of information about the radiographic technique itself stressed the necessity of performing a more comprehensive investigation in this field.

Scope of the Investigation

The purpose of this investigation is to establish the exposure technique for the radiographic examination of carbon fibre reinforced composites (samples 2 and 3 mm thick). This examination is performed with X-ray film and paper of different brands with different speed and graininess.

For this established technique the quality of the radiographs on different photographic material is investigated. For that purpose a special procedure is adopted (step wedge technique) because the conventional image quality indicators could not be used.

An attempt to produce artificial, calibrated defects failed, thus the detectability limit of defects was estimated from samples with natural defects.

The use of tungsten wires embedded in the samples permitted not only a determination of the detectability limit of metal inclusions, but also a test of the accuracy of dimensional measurements from radiographs.

Experimental Methods

Samples

Two types of samples were used. A commercial carbon fibre reinforced epoxy material, called pultrusion, was obtained (from the firm Courtaulds, England). It contains 60 vol% of continuous fibres, and has cross-sectional dimensions of 2×10 mm; this material was used as reference and for the step wedge.

A series of laboratory samples were fabricated from the epoxy LY 554/HY 554 (firm Ciba-Geigy, Denmark) and high modulus carbon fibres of diameter 8-9 μm (type HMS, from the firm Courtaulds, England). Continuous as well as short (~ 5 mm) fibres were used in volume fractions of 20-30%. The samples were fabricated in a simple leaky mould and the specimens were 15 mm wide and 3 mm thick. These samples had a somewhat irregular fibre distribution and contained several "natural" defects, mostly voids.

It was tried to produce voids of a known diameter by embedding a tungsten wire into the sample and thereafter by breaking the wire, which would produce a gap, simulating a natural void. Unfortunately, it was impossible to break the tungsten wire inside the sample.

A special series of laboratory samples were made with a single tungsten wire along their length. The samples contained 42 vol% of continuous carbon fibres, and were 10 mm wide and 2 mm thick. Wires of diameter 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 100 μm were introduced, and the specimens were used for the determination of measurement accuracy, and for the simulation of (metallic) inclusions.

X-ray Machine

All radiographs were taken with the constant potential Balteau Baltographe BE 50/20, with a 1 mm beryllium window, 0.5 mm focus, X-ray tube. This tube can be operated at a maximum load of 500 kV.mA in the region from 25 to 50 kV. From 15 to 25 kV a maximum current of 20 mA is allowed, whereas below 15 kV currents below 20 mA are possible (e.g. at 10 kV only 10 mA can be obtained).

X-ray Film and Paper

Radiographs were taken on different brands of X-ray film and paper, which have different speed and grain size of the photographic emulsion.

The following brands of Kodak Industrex X-ray films were tested (listed in order of decreasing speed and grain size): D, C, M, DR and SR (single coated). Agfa-Gevaert single coated Structurix D2 film was also used, which has a speed even lower than the Kodak SR film.

In many other fields of industrial radiography X-ray paper can be used [28] presenting the advantage of very high speed, low cost (1/3 of that of the film) and very short processing time. Therefore, it was decided to test radiographic paper, and the Kodak Industrex Instant 600 and Agfa-Gevaert Structurix IC paper were used. Short exposures of high contrast can be obtained only when using radiographic paper together with fluorescent intensifying screens. Therefore, for both brands of radiographic paper the Agfa-Gevaert Structurix IC type II screen was used.

Throughout the investigation it was attempted to produce radiographs of approximately equal optical density. The film densities were measured with the Macbeth transmission Quantalog densitometer, Model TD-100A, whereas paper densities were read by the Super Speedmaster reflection densitometer Model R 70 B of the Electric Systems Engineering Co. The two densitometers were used not only to control the overall density of the radiographs, but also in the assessment of the radiographic quality by the density contrast method. The accuracy of density readings of those densitometers is ± 0.01 .

Exposure Technique

Throughout the investigation a focus-film-distance of 50 cm was maintained. The comparison of radiographs obtained on different film brands was performed by producing radiographs of approximately constant densities. Such radiographs were obtained by using the constant exposure technique, as recommended by Ruault [29,30]. Thus a constant exposure of 100 m A min (10 mA, 10 min) was given and the voltage was chosen so as to give a constant density of the radiographs (for X-ray films $D_f \sim 2.0$, for radiographic paper $D_p \sim 1.0$).

Table I gives the voltages necessary to reach the above film and paper densities for the 2 and 3 mm thick samples.

Neither the X-ray film nor the paper could be exposed in the standard rigid X-ray cassettes. The front side of such a cassette, usually made of a 1 mm aluminium plate, attenuates very strongly the soft X-rays and changes its spectrum. Paper cassettes, which practically do not attenuate even soft X-rays, could not be used, because at very low voltages (about 10 kV) the fibrous structure of the paper was seen on the radiographs. For these reasons cassettes made of plastic foils were used.

To avoid the filtration effect of the cassette, which is normally interspaced between the specimen and the X-ray film, the specimen was placed directly on the film inside the cassette.

Table I. Exposure Technique

(10 mA; 10 min; 100 mAmin; FFD= 50 cm)

		Paper Film	Intensifying screen	kV	
				2 mm	3 mm
Paper	IC	600	IC II	11.25	12.00
			IC II	10.75	11.25
Film	D		0	10.00	10.50
	C		0	10.50	11.00
	A		0	10.75	11.50
	M		0	12.00	12.50
	DR		0	13.00	14.00
	SR		0	13.50	14.50
	D2S		0	15.25	17.00

To assure good contact between the specimen and the film a vacuum cassette was used.

The vacuum cassette was especially valuable when radiographic paper with an intensifying screen was used. Here perfect contact between the paper and the screen is essential (to avoid additional unsharpness), and this could be assured by the vacuum cassette. The fluorescent intensifying screen contains heavy metals, which considerably attenuate soft X-rays. Therefore, contrary to the normal radiographic practice, the screen was placed at the bottom of the cassette, its fluorescent surface facing the paper emulsion, and the specimen was placed on top of the paper inside the cassette, facing the X-ray tube. Thus a reversed picture was obtained on the paper.

Dimensional Measurement

Dimensions were measured from the radiographs with a projection microscope. Radiographs, recorded on X-ray film, were placed on the projector and magnified 10, 20, 50 or 100 times, and from the screen of the projection microscope interesting dimensions were directly read. A Nikon Profile Projector Model 6 CT with an accuracy of $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$ was used. Although it is possible to use the projector for reflection measurements it was not possible to read dimensions from paper radiographs, because of too low contrast on the microscope screen.

Results and Discussion

Radiographic Quality

It is common practice to assess the quality of radiographic picture by the use of the Image Quality Indicators (IQI). They are prescribed both by international (ISO) and by several national standards (e.g. BS, AFNOR, DIN, ASTM). The most commonly used IQI's consist of a set of wires, of different diameters, made of the same material as the object under examination. The IQI is placed atop on the radiation source side of the radiographed object and is exposed together with it. The diameter of the smallest wire, which can be seen on the radiograph (expressed in per cent of the object thickness) is a measure of the radiographic quality. Instead of wires sometimes plates with holes of different diameter are used.

It is not always possible to use the standard IQI, because it can be difficult or even impossible to fabricate them from the materials under examination. This is the case with carbon fibre reinforced plastics. Therefore another method for assessment of radiographic quality was adopted, which has previously proved useful in the quality control of nuclear fuel elements [31]. This method consists of using a step wedge made of the material to be examined as an IQI. In our case a 2 mm sample of the commercial carbon fibre composite (pultrusion) was ground down to several calibrated thicknesses. On four samples 16 steps were made, with the following reductions in thickness (expressed in μm and in per cent of the original 2 mm thickness):

10, 20, 35, 50, 60, 70, 115, 220, 270, 390, 480, 580, 710 μm
0.5;1.0;1.7;2.5;3.0;3.4;5.6;10.7;13.1;18.9;23.2;28.2;34.5 %
780, 880, 960 μm
37.9;42.7;46.6 %

The samples were radiographed on different X-ray films and papers (see fig. 1), and optical film or paper densities were measured with densitometer, for the 2 mm (100%) step and all the 16 steps with reduced thickness. Then the density difference $\Delta D_{\frac{1}{2}}$ was calculated and plotted against the thickness difference $\Delta_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (see fig. 2). As can be seen, thickness reductions greater than

Fig. 1. Radiograph of a Step Wedge

Fig. 2. Per Cent Density Contrast

1% could be detected on all X-ray films and on the 600 radiographic paper, whereas the 0.5% thickness difference was detectable only on the very fine grain Kodak R film.

In routine radiography densitometers are rarely used to detect density differences on actual radiographs. These are normally inspected by visual examination on special illuminators. Therefore, the step wedge densities were also assessed visually by three observers, who determined the smallest visible density difference on the radiographs. On all X-ray films and on the 600 radiographic paper all observers could distinguish the 1.7% thickness difference, and for the IC paper the 2.5% thickness difference was needed. Some observers could see the 1.0% or even the 0.5% thickness difference on the very fine grain X-ray films.

Measuring Accuracy

To assess the measuring accuracy of dimensions from radiographs the samples with tungsten wires were radiographed on all brands of X-ray film and paper; an example is shown on fig. 3. From the radiographs tungsten wire diameters were measured on the projection microscope (100 × magnification). It was not possible to use the projection microscope for measurements on the paper radiographs.

Fig. 3. Radiograph of 5, 10, 20 and 30 μm tungsten wires

Fig. 4 . Tungsten Wire Diameter Measurements

The measurements were performed by two observers and the results are shown on fig. 4. The largest deviation from the ideal (broken) line amounts to +60% and -10% for the 5 μm wire and drops to +6% and -1% for the 100 μm wire. The low measuring accuracy in the small diameter region is due to the measuring principle of the projection microscope itself. The measurement consists of aligning the measured contour seen on the screen with a line engraved on the screen. This line has a finite thickness and it is obvious that for objects of small dimensions the inaccuracy of correctly aligning the line on the screen with the object contour is greater.

Defect Detection

The best way to determine the detection limit of defects, which may occur in the material under examination, is to produce artificial defects of known, calibrated dimensions. The defects of interest would be voids or inclusions. Natural voids could be simulated by producing holes of known dimensions, which will show

on the radiographs as dark spots. Inclusions, made of a material with a higher attenuation to radiation, will be reproduced as light spots.

The detection limit was assessed from samples containing natural defects in the form of voids. Figure 5 shows a radiograph

Fig. 5. Radiograph of 3 mm samples with natural defects

Fig. 6. Natural defects in sample 5B

of several samples with natural defects. On sample 5B three defects were chosen (shown on fig. 6 in a 50 × enlargement), and their dimensions were measured from radiographs taken on the different X-ray film brands. The defect marked t_1 was the smallest, which could be detected on the projection microscope (it was invisible by direct reading of the radiographs with the naked eye). It had a diameter of about 100 μm and this can be considered as a detection limit for natural defects in the form of voids (in a 3 mm thick sample). The medium size defect (marked t_2 on fig. 6) had a diameter of about 200 μm , whereas the largest defect (t_3) was about 550 μm in diameter. The diameters of those three defects were measured on the projection microscope using enlargements of 10, 20 and 50 ×. The smallest defect (t_1) could not be detected on the fastest X-ray film (Kodak D), but was visible on all other films. The best measuring results could be obtained at 20 × magnification.

The detectability of defects in the form of inclusions of metals could be judged by the assessment of radiographs of the samples containing tungsten wires. As mentioned above even the thinnest wire (diameter 5 μm) could be clearly seen on all film radiographs. On paper radiographs the thinnest detectable wire was that of 20 μm .

Conclusions

From this investigation the following conclusions can be drawn:

1) Low voltage radiography with soft X-rays is particularly suitable for the non-destructive examination of carbon fibre reinforced composites.

2) For thin sections of such composites very low voltages are required (10-17 kV) and it is essential to use a beryllium window X-ray tubes with a focus as small as possible.

3) Use of fine grain X-ray films assures good defect detectability. The low speed of these films can be compensated by using relatively high voltages to obtain reasonable exposure times.

4) Use of high speed films or even radiographic paper (with fluorescent intensifying screens) can be recommended only if no high radiographic quality is required (e.g. in a preliminary examination, aimed at establishing the correct exposure technique).

5) Dimensions can be read from radiographs with a relatively high accuracy, if the boundaries are well defined such as at metallic inclusions.

6) It can be expected that natural defects in the form of voids can be detected if they are larger than 0.1 mm.

7) Inclusions, in the form of metallic materials, can be easily detected, even if they are so small as a 5 μm tungsten wire.

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